

Outcome Analysis of Patients with Extra Pulmonary Drug-Resistant Tuberculosis at The Nashik Nodal DRTB Centre

Komal Shah*, Bhavik Shah**

ABSTRACT

Background: As per Global tuberculosis report 2024 (1), India contributes 26% of Global TB incidence and 27% of MDR TB globally. Mortality due to TB (non HIV) was reported more than 3 lakhs (29% of global TB deaths). (2) Limited data exists on the prevalence and drug resistance patterns in extrapulmonary tuberculosis (EPTB). This study aims to assess the drug resistance patterns of Mycobacterium tuberculosis in EPTB cases and evaluate treatment outcomes.

Materials and Methods: This retrospective study was conducted to analyse patients diagnosed with extrapulmonary multidrug-resistant tuberculosis between April 2019 and March 2020. The objective was to assess the clinical profile and treatment response in these cases.

Results: A total of 54 patients were diagnosed with extrapulmonary drug-resistant TB within 1 year (April 2019 to March 2020). Of these, 66.6% were female, and 33.3% were male, with the most affected age group being 21-29 years (26.4%). Lymph node involvement was the most common manifestation followed by bones and joint involvement. Surprisingly, more than 70% patients were primary extrapulmonary DRTB patients with only 3 patients having history of TB contact. Rifampicin resistance was found in 74% of cases and 11% patients diagnosed as pre-XDR. Treatment yielded favorable outcomes in most patients with less than 10% mortality rate.

Conclusion: Among 54 EP-DRTB patients, 70% were primary cases—an unusual and notable finding. Despite this, treatment outcomes were positive, reflecting effective management at the Nodal DRTB Centre, Nashik.

INTRODUCTION

The WHO Global TB Report 2024 states that extrapulmonary TB accounted for 17% of the 7.5 million global TB cases in 2022, with a growing concern over drug-resistant forms. (1) India saw a 17.7% decline in TB incidence since 2015, yet continues to bear the highest burden globally. (2) Drug-resistant extrapulmonary TB poses a unique challenge in diagnosis and management, requiring intensified surveillance and tailored treatment strategies. This study aims to evaluate the clinical presentation and treatment outcomes of EP DR-TB under programmatic management at a nodal DRTB centre, Nashik.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This retrospective study was conducted at the Nodal Drug-Resistant Tuberculosis (DR-TB) Centre, Department of Respiratory Medicine, Dr. Vasantao Pawar Medical College, Nashik. The study included patients diagnosed with extrapulmonary multidrug-resistant (MDR) and extensively drug-resistant (XDR) tuberculosis between April 2019 and March 2020. Data were retrospectively extracted from patient records in accordance with the programmatic DR-TB management guidelines.

Inclusion Criteria:

Patients diagnosed with extrapulmonary MDR/XDR-TB and admitted between April 2019 and March 2020.

Exclusion Criteria:

Patients with incomplete medical records.

The primary aim was to determine the proportion of extrapulmonary drug-resistant TB cases and analyze their clinical profiles and treatment outcomes. Data were analyzed using appropriate statistical methods.

RESULTS

1) Demographic Variables:

From April 2019 to March 2020, 54 patients were diagnosed with extrapulmonary drug-resistant TB. Among them, 18 were male (33.33%) and 36 were female (66.66%). The most affected age group was 21-29 years (46.29%), followed by 10-20 years (25.92%). The least affected age group was 60-69 years (1.85%).

Fig.1 : Sex Distribution

*Associate Professor, respiratory medicine, Dr, Vasantao Pawar Medical College, Nashik

**Head of the Department of Critical Care, Ashoka Medicover Hospital, Nashik

Corresponding Author:

Komal Shah, Associate professor, respiratory medicine, Dr, Vasantao Pawar medical college, Nashik

Fig.2 : Age group distribution

2) Organ Involvement:

Lymph node involvement was the most common site, occurring in 38 cases (70.37%), followed by bone involvement (13%). Resistance in breast abscesses and the central nervous system was also observed.

Fig.3 : Organ Involvement

3) History of Tuberculosis:

Eight patients had a history of pulmonary TB, and seven had a history of extrapulmonary TB. Three patients had known contact with DS/DR-TB cases.

4) Drug Resistance Pattern:

Among the study population, 74% were resistant to rifampicin, while 11.11% were classified as pre-XDR with fluoroquinolone resistance. Resistance to fluoroquinolones and isoniazid was equally observed.

Fig.4 : Drug Resistance Pattern

5) Treatment Outcomes:

- Treatment completion: 42 patients (77.77%)
- Mortality during treatment: 5 patients (9.25%)
- Defaulters: 5 patients (9.25%)
- Lost to follow-up: 1 patient (1.85%)
- Transferred out: 1 patient (1.85%)

Fig.4 : Outcome

DISCUSSION

The proportion of extrapulmonary DR-TB cases in our study was 8.85%, higher than the 4.4% reported in previous studies. (3) The expansion of universal drug susceptibility testing has contributed to improved detection of DR-TB cases and resistance patterns. We also noticed higher rates of primary extrapulmonary DRTB cases than in previous studies. (5,6)

The majority of EP DR-TB cases were seen in younger patients (72%), with a higher prevalence in females (66%), aligning with findings from other studies. Lymph node involvement was the most common site (70.37%) same as other studies (7), followed by bone TB, differing from previous studies by the National Institute for Research in Tuberculosis (NIRT). (8)

Resistance to rifampicin was the most common, followed by fluoroquinolone resistance, differing from studies that reported higher pre-XDR fluoroquinolone resistance. HIV co-infection was found in four cases (7.40%), with one patient initiating treatment during pregnancy.

The treatment success rate was 77.77%, with 9.25% mortality and defaulter rates.

The retrospective nature of this study limited the ability to assess reasons for treatment default and mortality causes.

CONCLUSION

This study highlights the significant burden of extrapulmonary DR-TB, particularly in younger, female patients even in absence of prior history of TB or significant TB contact (i.e primary extrapulmonary DRTB). While most patients responded well to treatment, the high rates of rifampicin resistance and pre-XDR-TB require enhanced surveillance and individualized treatment strategies. Continued efforts to reduce treatment default and mortality are essential to improving outcomes in this population.

REFERENCES

1. Who global report 2024 <https://www.who.int/teams/global-tuberculosis-programme/tb-reports>
2. Paramasivan CN, Venkataraman P (2004) Drug resistance in tuberculosis in India. *Indian J Med Res* 120: 377–386.
3. Desai U, Joshi JM. Extrapulmonary drug-resistant tuberculosis at a drug-resistant tuberculosis center, Mumbai: Our experience – Hope in the midst of despair! *Lung India* 2019;36:3-7.
4. Diriba G, Kebede A, Tola HH, Yenew B, Moga S, Addise D, et al. (2020) Molecular characterization and drug resistance patterns of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex in extrapulmonary tuberculosis patients in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. *PLoS ONE* 15(12): e0243493.
5. Waghmare MA, Utpat K, Joshi JM. Treatment outcome of drug-resistant pulmonary tuberculosis under programmatic management of multi-drug resistant tuberculosis, at a tertiary care center in Mumbai. *Med J DY Patil Univ* 2017;10:41-5.
6. Dalal A, Pawaskar A, Das M, Desai R, Prabhudesai P, Chhajed P, et al. Resistance patterns among multidrug-resistant tuberculosis patients in greater metropolitan Mumbai: Trends over time. *PLoS On* 2015;10:e0116798
7. Suryawanshi SL, Shewade HD, Nagaraja SB, Nair SA, Parmar M. Unfavourable outcomes among patients with MDR-TB on the standard 24-month regimen in Maharashtra, India. *Public Health Action* 2017; 7:116-22.
8. Dusthacker A, Sekar G, Chidambaram S, Kumar V, Mehta P, Swaminathan S, et al. Drug resistance among extrapulmonary TB patients: Six years experience from a supranational reference laboratory. *Indian J Med Res* 2015;142:568-74.